

Evolving Patterns of Deprivation, Diversity, and Mode Share in Saskatoon's Urban Core and Housing Accelerator Fund Areas (2006–2021)

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines socio-economic and mobility changes in Saskatoon between 2006 and 2021. We focus on areas targeted by the City of Saskatoon approved Housing Accelerator Fund (HAF) regions and the urban core. We adapted the Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation (CIMD) to assess change and evaluate whether earlier trends positioned current HAF areas as those most in need of redevelopment, improved transit, and densification. Statistical analysis shows rising economic dependency and car reliance citywide, alongside declining active and transit commuting. Compared to the rest of the city, HAF zones show higher deprivation, though 15-year changes indicate greater improvements in HAF area.

1. Introduction

Canada is currently experiencing an acute housing affordability crisis, that presents one of the greatest national challenges (Housing, Infrastructure and Communities Canada, n.d.). This crisis is characterized by persistently high home prices, rising rents, and declining affordability across regions (CMHC, 2025). In response, the federal government launched the Housing Accelerator Fund (HAF) in 2023, a \$4 billion initiative designed to increase housing supply through planning reforms and financial incentives. Yet, research challenges the premise behind the HAF, arguing that increasing supply alone will not slow price or rent growth. Instead, new construction, densification, and gentrification will have added units at above-median cost, while affordable stock continues to decline (Pomeroy, 2022). Under the definition of Canada Mortgage and Housing Corporation (CMHC), housing is considered “affordable” if it costs less than 30% of a household’s before-tax income (CMHC, 2018).

These concerns become even more relevant given that one of the core HAF requirements for additional per-unit funding is building multi-family homes within 800 meters of active public transportation (CMHC, 2023). In Saskatoon, this area is called the Transit Development Area (TDA), the zone in which HAF changes have been applied (City of Saskatoon, n.d.). While walkable access to transit is a central sustainability objective, its broader consequences are ambiguous. Research shows that proximity to quality public transit often results in rising home values and rent (Zuk et al., 2018; Beaudoin & Tyndall, 2023). Beyond housing cost, transit-oriented development can also induce gentrification, displacement, and other negative effects for vulnerable populations (Dawkins & Moeckel, 2016).

This research seeks to understand whether neighbourhoods prioritized under the HAF have experienced different trajectories in socio-economic deprivation and diversity compared to the rest of the city in the years preceding HAF funding. We also include a comparison of Saskatoon’s urban core more generally. The HAF analysis explores to what extent these areas are already in a trajectory to achieve HAF’s density objective, even without the implementation of HAF policies. By analyzing socio-economic trends and mode-share changes in these areas from 2006 to 2021, the study will provide insights into the impacted populations and if the housing and transit implementations will positively impact Saskatoon residents most in need of such interventions.

This work contributes to current academic and policy debates in several ways. First, it integrates spatial analysis of four CIMD dimensions, including ethno-cultural diversity, economic dependency, situational vulnerability, and residential instability with mode share and economic diversity, enabling a multi-dimensional assessment of urban change. Second, it differentiates between HAF-targeted areas, urban core, and broader parts of the city (non-Urban Core, non-HAF area) to explore emerging patterns and whether new federal interventions are related to historic urban trends. Third, it provides longitudinal, comparative evidence from one mid-sized Canadian community, many of which are understudied in housing policy research.

2. Methods & Data

This study used multiple data sources. The Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation (CIMD) socio-economic variables, as well as transportation mode share, were sourced from the Statistics Canada 2006 and 2021 Census at the dissemination area (DA) level. We adapted CIMD’s original variables for the Prairies (Statistics Canada, 2023) to ensure comparability between 2006 and 2021, since several 2021 indicators are not available in the 2006 Census. The substituted variables were selected to preserve the conceptual structure of CIMD’s four dimensions while allowing consistent measurement across years. Specifically, we replaced median value of dwellings (\$) with average value of dwellings (\$) in the residential instability dimension; removed the religious affiliation in both years in ethno-cultural diversity dimension; replaced children under 6 years old with the children 0-4 years old category in economic dependency dimension; and substituted proportion of people receiving government transfers with proportion of households spending more than 30% of

income on shelter costs in the situational vulnerability dimension. All variables used to compute the scores and the CIMD are shown in Figure 1. Since DAs experienced significant spatial changes in the 15 years of this study, an equal-sized (0.01 km²) hexagon layer was created to allow for temporal comparison of common spatial units in 2006 and 2021. To ensure that data represent only inhabited areas of Saskatoon, we used parcel-level land-use data to remove all non-residential parcels from the analysis. To harmonize

Notes: red outlines indicate variables that were substituted; hatched fill indicates variables that were removed.

Figure 1. Variables used to construct CIMD dimensions for Saskatoon, 2006–2021

2006 and 2021 DA-level variables to the hexagon grid, we used residential-area-based weighting (Reibel & Agrawal, 2007). For each DA-hexagon intersection, we calculated the proportion of the DA’s residential land area contained in the hexagon and applied this ratio to all DA-level variables. Weighted values from all intersecting DAs were then summed to produce a single value per hexagon, from where the proportions for each variable were calculated. For each CIMD dimension (i.e., ethno-cultural diversity, residential instability, situational vulnerability, and economic dependency) we standardized the component variables using z-scores, summed them to form a

composite dimension score, and converted the resulting scores into quantiles for comparability and interpretation.

Drawing on ecological and economic applications of the Shannon index (e.g. Templet, 1999; Nagendra, 2002, Murgante et al., 2024), we apply it to measure amenity and service-type diversity. The index was calculated using the DMTI Spatial Enhanced Points of Interest (EPOI) dataset and aggregated to the hexagon level. EPOIs belonging to service- and amenity-related SIC major groups (e.g., retail, food services, personal services, business services, health services, social services, educational services, amusement and recreation, and lodging) were included, based on the DMTI Spatial SIC taxonomy (DMTI Spatial Inc., 2007). The Shannon Index is calculated as:

Where:

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^R p_i \ln(p_i)$$

H' =Shannon Diversity Index

R =total number of SIC groups

p_i =proportion of POIs belonging to SIC major group i ($p_i = n_i / N$, where n_i is the count of POIs in group i and N is the total count of POIs).

Figure 2. Saskatoon study zones: UC, CGA, TDA.

For analysis, we used the Transit Development Area (TDA) (within 800 meters radius of BRT), Bus Rapid Transit Corridor Growth Area (CGA) (within 250 meters of BRT), and Urban Core (nine core neighbourhoods of Saskatoon that serve as historical and commercial heart of the city with the highest employment concentration). All the spatial zone shapefiles were obtained from the City of Saskatoon.

Under the HAF amendments, CGA land uses allow for increased height and density, whereas TDA, that lies outside CGA, allows multi-unit dwellings up to 4 storeys (City of Saskatoon, 2024). Therefore, we isolated the portion of the TDA that lies outside the CGA using ArcGIS Pro. We then assigned hexagons to each zone based on the location of their centroids, generating a separate “TDA-outside-CGA” zone. Each spatial zone (CGA, TDA-outside-CGA, non-CGA, Urban Core, and non-Urban Core) was

operationalized in a dummy variable indicating whether a hexagon fell within that zone. All zones are shown in Figure 2. MANOVA, ANOVA, t-tests, and Tukey post-hoc tests were used to determine whether changes between 2006 and 2021 in the overall CIMD, its four dimensions, mode share, and economic diversity indicators, differed significantly across the spatial zones.

3. Results

For this section, summary statistics were developed for six zones: Corridor Growth Area (CGA, 250m around BRT line) vs. outer area (non-CGA); Transit Development Area (TDA, 800m around BRT, includes CGA) vs. outer area (non-TDA); and Urban Core (UC) vs. outer area (non-UC).

3.1. Summary statistics

As shown in Table 1, across all zones (UC, TDA, and CGA), mode share patterns show a consistent decline in transit and active transportation between 2006 and 2021, accompanied by greater reliance on automotive travel. In the UC, transit use fell by 3% and active travel by 7%, while non-UC areas had smaller declines (1% and 2%, respectively). The outer areas remained substantially more car dependent. As can be seen in Appendix C, “matched means” reveal that UC residents used cars 21% less than outer-area residents in 2006 and 13% less in 2021, but the UC experienced a sharper increase in car reliance over time (+9%), a shift that may partially reflect pandemic-related changes in travel behaviour with former transit users choosing to drive. The difference

between matched- and expanded-means shows structural differences in the sample: the expanded 2021 dataset includes newly developed peripheral areas that had no equivalent hexagons in 2006, all of which are overwhelmingly car-oriented and as a result pull 2021-expanded averages toward higher driving and lower transit/active shares.

CIMD patterns show the spatial structure of disadvantage: UC areas show substantially higher (worse) CIMD scores than the outer areas, but UC deprivation index declined between 2006 and 2021, while outer areas experienced a slight increase, suggesting redistribution (or displacement of population) rather than elimination of socio-economic problems. Component scores indicate that urban cores are characterized by higher residential instability, situational vulnerability, and economic dependency, all of which decreased modestly over time.

The TDA vs. non-TDA comparison follows similar trends: non-TDA peripheral areas show the highest car mode share (over 90%) and minimal transit use (<5%) in both years; both TDA and non-TDA saw decline in active and public modes of transit, while car reliance increased – a trend, followed in all other study areas. CIMD differences again show improvement inside TDAs and worsening in outer areas, though CIMD component means are closer to zero, with notably lower residential instability and ethno-cultural diversity in non-TDA zones. The CGA vs. non-CGA comparison shows that transit use inside CGA areas

	Mean diff (matched, 2006-2021)	Mean diff (expanded, 2006-2021)
car (UC)	9%	
car (non-UC)	1%	2%
car (TDA)	3%	1%
car (non-TDA)	1%	1%
car (CGA)	4%	4%
car (non-CGA)	2%	3%
active (UC)	-7%	
active (non-UC)	-2%	-3%
active (TDA)	-4%	-1%
active (non-TDA)	-2%	0
active (CGA)	-5%	-5%
active (non-CGA)	-2%	-3%
transit (UC)	-3%	
transit (non-UC)	-1%	-1%
transit (TDA)	-1%	0
transit (non-TDA)	-2%	0
transit (CGA)	-1%	-1%
transit (non-CGA)	-2%	-2%
CIMD (UC)	-0.24	
CIMD (non-UC)	0.03	-0.67
CIMD (TDA)	-0.09	-0.41
CIMD (non-TDA)	0.09	-0.71
CIMD (CGA)	-0.11	-0.24
CIMD (non-CGA)	0.03	-0.69
ethno-cultural diversity (UC)	-0.36	
ethno-cultural diversity (non-UC)	-0.21	-0.14
ethno-cultural diversity (TDA)	-0.19	-0.15
ethno-cultural diversity (non-TDA)	-0.29	-0.16
ethno-cultural diversity (CGA)	-0.14	-0.11
ethno-cultural diversity (non-CGA)	-0.28	-0.18
residential instability (UC)	-0.15	
residential instability (non-UC)	0.03	0.09
residential instability (TDA)	-0.03	-0.03
residential instability (non-TDA)	0.03	0.14
residential instability (CGA)	-0.03	-0.03
residential instability (non-CGA)	0.01	0.08
situational vulnerability (UC)	-0.12	
situational vulnerability (non-UC)	0.02	0.03
situational vulnerability (TDA)	0.01	-0.01
situational vulnerability (non-TDA)	-0.02	0.01
situational vulnerability (CGA)	0.01	0.00
situational vulnerability (non-CGA)	-0.01	-0.01
economic dependency (UC)	-0.11	
economic dependency (non-UC)	0.29	0.23
economic dependency (TDA)	0.12	0.07
economic dependency (non-TDA)	0.35	0.31
economic dependency (CGA)	0.07	0.04
economic dependency (non-CGA)	0.29	0.24

Note. Values in gray cells did not change from “expanding” the dataset. 2006 matched values and 2006 expanded values are equal. Matched dataset represents values from DAs that only existed in 2006. Expanded dataset adds values from 2021 DAs.

Table 1. Mean change in mode share, CIMD, and CIMD scores across Saskatoon study zones: UC, non-UC, CGA, non-CGA, TDA, non-TDA.

remained relatively stable, while outer-area transit use halved over the periods, and car reliance remained consistently higher outside the CGA (8% higher in 2006; 7% higher in 2021). CIMD trends in CGA areas show the pattern observed in UC and TDA results – declining deprivation

index in central zones and slightly rising deprivation at the periphery – indicating possible areas of minor gentrification or displacement of residents.

To understand if socio-economic and mode share patterns align with changes in economic

Figure 3. Change in average economic activity, 2007 – 2024

activity, we measure average changes in POI counts by zone as a proxy of economic activity. Across all three zones, the expanded dataset shows slightly greater increases in economic activity than the matched sample (see Figure 3), but the overall spatial pattern is consistent. The UC experienced the largest increase in POIs between 2007 and 2024 (6.48 average), while growth within CGA and TDA was modest (2.36 and 1.28, respectively). Outside these zones average POI change was close to zero, emphasizing that growth was highly

concentrated within urban core and policy-prioritized areas. Comparing changes in Shannon diversity from 2007 to 2024, no significant differences were found for the TDA or CGA ($p > 0.4$), however, the UC showed a small but statistically significant decrease in diversity ($\Delta = -0.071$, $p < 0.05$). It is important to note that Shannon index calculates economic diversity change within each hexagon and focuses on inclusion of POI that belong to different SIC groups.

3.2. Statistical analysis

MANOVA indicated significant multivariate differences across HAF zones (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.845$, $F(16, 1686) = 9.26$, $p < 0.001$). For the UC, multivariate differences were also significant (Wilks' $\Lambda = 0.781$, $F(8, 844) = 29.60$, $p < 0.001$). ANOVA was used to identify which variables showed statistically significant differences across HAF zone group: CGA, TDA-outside-CGA, and neither. As seen in Table 2, change in CIMD, ethno-cultural diversity, economic dependency, and car and active mode-shares showed significant difference ($p < 0.05$). An Independent t-test was used to test UC vs. non-UC differences (Table 3). UC had greater improvements in CIMD, residential instability, situational vulnerability, and economic dependency than non-UC areas, with a larger increase in car mode share (+7.53%) and a decline in active mode share (-4.79%).

Variable (HAF)	P-value	Signif.
CIMD change	<0.001	***
Ethno-cultural diversity change	<0.05	*
Residential instability change	0.062	ns
Situational vulnerability change	0.799	ns
Economic dependency change	<0.001	***
Car mode share change	<0.001	***
Active mode share change	<0.001	***
Transit mode share change	0.559	ns

Table 2. ANOVA results for HAF zone group

Variable (UC)	Mean diff (UC-non-UC)	P-value	Signif.
CIMD change	-0.27	<0.001	***
Ethno-cultural diversity change	-0.15	0.079	ns
Residential instability change	-0.18	<0.001	***
Situational vulnerability change	-0.14	<0.001	***
Economic dependency change	-0.40	<0.001	***
Car mode share change	7.53%	<0.001	***
Active mode share change	-4.79%	<0.001	***
Transit mode share change	-2%	0.001	***

Table 3. t-test results: Urban Core vs. non-Urban Core

Tukey post-hoc tests were conducted to determine pairwise differences and their direction for the HAF zone groups. Tukey results showed that the largest 2006-2021 change occurred between CGA and Neither, which was significant for all variables (see Table 4). TDA and Neither pair were significantly different in CIMD and mode-share change. Transit mode-share change was not included in post-hoc, since it did not show significance for zone difference in univariate

Variable	Comparison	diff	P adj	Signif.
CIMD change	Neither-CGA	0.177	<0.01	**
	TDA (outside CGA) - CGA	0.048	0.703	ns
	TDA-Neither	-0.128	<0.05	*
Ethno-cultural diversity change	Neither-CGA	-0.215	<0.01	**
	TDA (outside CGA) - CGA	-0.074	0.651	ns
	TDA-Neither	0.140	0.114	ns
Economic dependency change	Neither-CGA	0.297	<0.001	***
	TDA (outside CGA) - CGA	0.045	0.782	ns
	TDA-Neither	-0.252	<0.001	***
Car mode share change	Neither-CGA	-2.25%	<0.01	**
	TDA (outside CGA) - CGA	0.032%	0.999	ns
	TDA-Neither	2.28%	<0.001	***
Active mode share change	Neither-CGA	3.49%	<0.001	***
	TDA (outside CGA) - CGA	2.27%	<0.001	***
	TDA-Neither	-1.22%	<0.05	*

Note. "Neither -CGA/TDA" refers to areas that are neither within CGA or TDA in contrast to CGA/TDA. "TDA (outside CGA) -CGA" refers to areas in TDA but outside the CGA in contrast to CGA.

Table 4. Tukey HSD Pairwise Comparisons for HAF Zones

ANOVA, which further emphasizes the citywide, almost uniformly low transit usage. Tukey results did not indicate difference between TDA and CGA significant for any variables.

4. Discussion & Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that HAF-designated areas and Urban Cores of Saskatoon experienced significantly different trajectories in the change of socio-economic characteristics compared to the rest of the city. These areas consistently exhibited higher levels of deprivation, residential instability, economic dependency, and situational vulnerability between 2006 and 2021, though they also experienced faster and more positive improvements over time. In contrast, all areas saw increases in car dependency and slight declines in active and transit mode shares, highlighting a city-wide shift toward automobile reliance despite socio-economic gains in priority zones.

Improvements within the areas investigated, alongside worsening conditions on the outskirts, may indicate displacement or minor gentrification (Zuk et al., 2018). These findings suggest that while current interventions support those in need within priority zones, complementary measures targeting the outer areas, such as expanded transit access and city-wide affordable housing policies, will be needed in the future to ensure equitable benefits across the city and to prevent displacement or uneven socio-economic outcomes (Pomeroy, 2022). We did not find patterns that would certainly point out gentrification, so the future consequences of BRT development and densification that HAF brings remain ambiguous for Saskatoon. It is important to note that 2021 Canadian Census may partially represent socio-economic characteristics of COVID-19 period, which could influence observed patterns and limit the direct applicability of some findings to typical, non-pandemic conditions.

This study also serves as a foundation for future research. We will expand the analysis by including housing stock, accessibility measures, a gentrification index, and by implementing regression modelling to shed light on the causal pathways of HAF contribution to either improving or worsening of current housing affordability situation. We also intend to increase our data sample to 15 Canadian cities of varying sizes to compare how communities differ in their socioeconomic and mode share shifts of HAF-dedicated areas and Urban Cores.

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Appendix A Mode Share Change Maps

Figure A1

Active Mode Share Comparison in Saskatoon: 2006 vs. 2021

Figure A2

Car Mode Share Comparison in Saskatoon: 2006 vs. 2021

Appendix B Socio-Economic Maps

Figure B1

Canadian Index of Multiple Deprivation in Saskatoon: 2006 vs. 2021

Figure B2

Residential Instability in Saskatoon: 2006 vs. 2021

Appendix C Comparison of Transit and Socio-Economic Variables Mean Value

Figure C1

Comparison of mode share, CIMD, and CIMD scores across Saskatoon study zones: UC vs. outer (non-UC), CGA vs. outer (non-CGA), and TDA vs. outer (non-TDA) in 2006 and 2021.

